

The church of Transfiguration of Savior, at Nomitsi, southern Messinia (Outer Mani), Peloponnese, Greece

also known as "Byzantine/Orthodox Christian church"

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The church is one of the most important byzantine monuments of southern Peloponnese, in terms of its architecture, wall paintings, relief decoration. Its initial phase of construction is dated in the end of 12th - beginning of the 13th century. An extensive use of various brick ornaments stand out in its exterior: "cloisonné masonry", checkerboard and rosette patterns, dentil courses and eaves, relief slabs. The interior surfaces are covered by at least two phases of painted decoration; probably one byzantine, very damaged, and one that is today more visible, of post-byzantine time, dated in the 16th-17th century. The church is decorated also by relief decoration in marble, set in pieces or as ensembles such as the arched screen (templon) and the capitals of columns. As a building, it stands out of high artistic and archaeological value, as a well- representative example of middle byzantine architectural culture.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Nomitsi, Messinia (Outer Mani), Peloponnese, southern Greece

Region tags: Greece, Mani, Messinia

Nomitsi, a village existing probably from ancient era, with a continuous habitation up to present day. A large number of byzantine and post-byzantine churches are still preserved within its setting.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: see bibliography

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/1/eh151.jsp?obj_id=1708 (Greek Ministry of Culture/ Odysseas)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: hillside, road

Notes: The church is built at the lowest point of a hillside, right opposite to the central road leading from Messinai to Laconia. This route is believed to have been used be from ancient times

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The church is situated between two significant (in terms of local archaeology and history) villages, Nomitsi and Thalames.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: the central road leading from Messinia to Laconia, meaning from north-west to south-east of the Peloponnese. The route is believed to have been in use already from ancient times.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The church is situated in close proximity of two villages, Nomitsi and Thalames.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: the byzantine church and next to it, a contemporary cemetery

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: domed cross-in-square

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: burial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Christ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: probably it was sponsored by common people, inhabitants of the village

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: probably it was sponsored by inhabitants of the village

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: probably all the above but nothing is certain

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– I don't know

↳ Sand
– I don't know

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– I don't know

Notes: in all probability wood was used for structural reasons but nothing is preserved

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: extensive use of fired clay (brick)

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: brick, carved marble, mortars and plasters

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: wall paintings, sculptures, brick

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

Notes: a) brick bands and patterns (checkerboard, rosettes, dentil courses and eaves, b) carved and inscribed reliefs (slabs, pieces)

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

Notes: wall paintings, relief decoration

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: some sculptured pieces can be removed

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: The painted decoration includes scenes of Christ's Life, saints, prelates and monks' figures.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, in scenes of his Life

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Mother of God, Saints, Apostles

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: soldiers, common people

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Sheep (?) in the scene of Nativity of Christ and others in reliefs

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: there also inscriptions painted or engraved (possibly) and reliefs

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: there are animals depicted, probably related to myths of ancient Greek writer Aesopus

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: rosettes

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: there are probably two phases of wall paintings, one byzantine and the one that is most visible today, dated in the 16th-17th century.

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: there are scenes of Christ's Life

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: the iconographic program its entity reflects typical doctrinal issues of Orthodox Christian faith

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: serving as a) commemoration of persons or donations b) identification of figures

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: there are also multiple dates included in the body of the inscriptions

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: brick and relief (see other entries)

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: big - shaped, occasionally with intense expression

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: both in painted and carved (relief) decoration

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Christ, Mother of God, Saints-Apostles

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: there is the scene of the Descent in Hell (Anastasis of Christ)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: relief with a cross

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: figures of prelates, apostles and saints

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: there are scenes of Christ's performing miracles but they are very damaged

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A contemporary cemetery is located opposite the church

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: not regularly

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: not often

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: A recent restoration performed by the local Ephorate of Antiquities of

Messinia took place in recent years

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: probably only at the commemoration feast of Christ's Transfiguration (4th of August)

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: The building is declared and operated as a monument

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: the local Archaeological Service, the Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia, of the Greek Ministry of Culture

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: It is declared as a monument

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The church of Transfiguration of Savior, at Nomitsi, southern Messinia (Outer Mani), Peloponnese, Greece, Drandakis, Nikolaos. *Byzantine Sculptures of Mani*. Athens: Archaeologike Etaireia, 2002.

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